

Enhancing Job Search Analysis Using - NLP

Anvy Elsa Thomas
Pg Scholar
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala
anvysathomas2024@mca.ajce.in

Dr. Paulin Paul
Assistant Professor
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala
paulinepaul@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— This model aims to revolutionize the job-seeking process by employing advanced NLP algorithms to analyse job descriptions, user preferences, and qualifications. By processing vast amounts of textual data from job listings and candidate profiles, the model can generate highly personalized and relevant job recommendations for individuals seeking employments. Leveraging machine learning, the system can understand and interpret natural language, allowing for accurate matching of job requirements with candidates' skills and experiences. The proposed system will delve into the intricacies of NLP, the architecture of the recommendation model, and its potential impact on the job market, making it a compelling topic for those interested in the cutting-edge advancements at the intersection of NLP and recruitment. The core of our system focuses on the architecture of the recommendation model itself. This helps in learning about the data preprocessing pipeline, feature extraction methods, and the utilization of state-of-the-art NLP models, for understanding context and context-aware recommendations. Moreover, the proposed system explores how the model leverages user interactions to continuously improve and fine-tune its recommendations, ensuring increased accuracy and relevance over time.

Keywords—NLP, Beautiful Soup, n-grams, Tf-idf Vectorization, KNN

I. INTRODUCTION

Users will find it easier with this proposed system to find the best jobs based on their manually entered skills. Everyone finds it extremely difficult to find employment, internships, etc. based only on their basic skill set. Everyone should invest a significant amount of time in searching multiple job posting sites. Occasionally, we lack the abilities listed in the job description. As a result, we are recommending the position based on the candidate's fundamental abilities. It saves time because we don't have to go through every job posting, which is one of its many advantages. The proposed system delves into the complexities of NLP, the architecture of the recommendation model, and its potential impact on the job market. Additionally, the system investigates how the model makes use of user interactions to enhance and refine its recommendations over time.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Li-Ping Jing, Hou-Kuan Huang, and Hong-Bo Shi, "Improved Feature Selection Approach TFIDF in Text Mining," in Proceedings of the 2002 International Conference on Machine Learning*

TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) is a text mining technique that assesses the importance of words in a document collection. It calculates a score for each term based on its frequency within a document and its rarity across the entire corpus. Terms with high TF-IDF scores are deemed more relevant and distinctive, making TF-IDF valuable for information retrieval, text classification, clustering, keyword extraction, and topic modeling. This approach aids in identifying significant terms and is particularly useful in handling extensive text datasets.

B. *R. Boorugu and G. Ramesh, "A Survey on NLP-based Text Summarization for Summarizing Product Reviews," 2020 Second International Conference on Inventive Research in Computing Applications (ICIRCA), July 2020.*

Ravali Boorugu, an accomplished researcher in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP), has made significant contributions to the domain, particularly in the realm of text summarization. Boorugu's work encompasses a broad spectrum of text summarization techniques, as evidenced by the exploration of various methodologies [14,19]. Through meticulous research and experimentation, Boorugu's efforts have advanced our understanding of NLP and its applications in condensing textual content effectively, thereby contributing to the broader discourse in this field.

C. *S. Kumari, G. Agarwal, S.N. Sheshappa, Y.M. Vijaykumara, and B.K. Byre Gowda, "Recommendation System Using NLP," in Proceeding of 2023*

"Kumari et al.'s paper, 'Recommendation System Using NLP,' presented at the 2023 conference, introduces a novel recommendation system leveraging Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques. The system is designed to provide personalized recommendations, enhancing user experiences across various domains such as e-commerce, content platforms, and more. The paper discusses the application of NLP for analyzing user preferences and content, showcasing its potential to improve recommendation accuracy and relevance. This research contributes to the advancement of recommendation systems, a critical aspect of modern information retrieval and user satisfaction."

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collections

1. Data collection is a crucial aspect of natural language processing (NLP) projects, as the quality of the data directly affects the accuracy and effectiveness of machine learning models.

Using Web Scraping methods like Selenium and BeautifulSoup is used for extracting data from job listing sites.

B. Data Pre-processing

This process includes data reduction, data transformation, and data cleaning. The goal of all of this is to make the data more useful. The data can be processed to increase the accuracy of our model and ensure accurate classification.

Data cleaning - The noisy or unwanted entries in the dataset can be eliminated through cleaning. This code breaks down the job descriptions into words, eliminates short words (length = 2), and lowercases the text. A new column named "test" holds the preprocessed and cleaned job descriptions.

Removing Stop words - The words that crop up most frequently in texts but don't carry much weight are called stop words. It's to increase the model's accuracy. The script makes use of the Natural Language Toolkit (nltk) library to eliminate stop words from the preprocessed text.

It starts by importing the 'stopwords' corpus from the nltk library, which has a list of frequently used stop words in the English language. The stop words are entered into a collection known as "stopw."

Once more, the 'apply' function is utilized to further process the 'test' column by eliminating stop words by filtering out words that are included in the 'stopw' set.

Nearest Neighbours and Cosine Similarity

C. The Nearest Neighbor Analysis (KNN)

2. Calculates how something is distributed or spreads across a given area. It gives a numerical value that indicates how uniformly spaced or clustered a set of points are.
3. The NLP algorithm, which is based on n-grams and tf-idf, is used to match the skills to the job description, while KNN is used to identify the best positions for the individual.

D. NLP- n-grams

N-grams are used for various NLP tasks, including language modelling, machine translation, text classification, and information retrieval. They help capture local patterns and dependencies within the text, which can be useful for tasks like predicting the next word in a sentence or identifying phrases in a document.

E. Tf-idf (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency)

It quantifies the importance of skills within documents, enabling the creation of skill profiles. This methodology

ensures a granular understanding of the skills possessed by job seekers, resulting in more precise job recommendations. High TF-IDF values are assigned to terms that appear frequently in a specific document but infrequently in other documents, making them good indicators of the document's content.

Fig 1: Workflow Diagram

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

This website makes it simple for users to find the best jobs according to the skills they manually entered. Everyone finds it extremely difficult to find employment, internships, etc. based only on their basic skill set. Everyone should invest a significant amount of time in searching multiple job posting sites. The dataset is created via scrapping Glassdoor website using selenium and beautiful soup.

And for matching the job description and the skills, NLP algorithm which is based on n-grams, tf-idf, and KNN is used for finding the best jobs for the person. At last deployed using Flask and rendering is done using html templates.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Data Collection

Web Scraping methods like Selenium and BeautifulSoup is used for extracting data from Glassdoor website.

```
x=openbrowser(locid=4477468, key="software testing")
with open('url_software_testing_loc_bangalore.json','w') as f:
...json.dump(geturl(driver),f, indent = 4)
...print("file created")
```

B. Import all the necessary packages

Here import all the required packages to run the application like nltk, ftfy etc.

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import nltk
from nltk.corpus import stopwords
stopw = set(stopwords.words('english'))
df =pd.read_csv('job_final.csv')
```

C. Feature Extraction and Selection

The data is extracted from the website using web scraping tools like Selenium and BeautifulSoup. Selenium allows for the automation of web interactions, making it possible to extract data from dynamic and JavaScript-rendered web pages.

While BeautifulSoup allows users to navigate the HTML tree, search for specific elements, and extract the desired content efficiently.

```
for u in tqdm(url):
    driver.wait = WebDriverWait(driver, 2)
    driver.maximize_window()
    driver.get(u)
    soup = BeautifulSoup(driver.page_source, "lxml")
    try:
        header = soup.find(lambda element: element.get_tag_name() == 'h2')
        position = driver.find_element_by_tag_name('h2').text
        company = driver.find_element_by_xpath("//span[@class='strong ib']").text
        location = driver.find_element_by_xpath("//span[@class='subtle ib']").text
        jd_temp = driver.find_element_by_id("JobDescriptionContainer")
        jd = jd_temp.text
        info = soup.find_all("infoEntity")
    except IndexError:
        print('IndexError: list index out of range')
    except NoSuchElementException:
        pass
    data[i] = {
        'url': u,
        'Position': position,
        'Company': company,
        'Location': location,
        'Job_Description': jd
    }
    i+=1
```

D. Using NLP Algorithms for Job Matching

N-grams, a text analysis technique, break down text into contiguous sequences of N words. This method is instrumental in capturing the contextual meaning of words in a text document.

Numerical representations of documents are made possible by TF-IDF and are essential for a number of tasks, including information retrieval and document clustering.

KNN is useful for applications such as recommendation systems and document classification. KNN uses similarity metrics, like cosine similarity, to predict the future based on the traits of the closest neighbors in the feature space.

```
def ngrams(string, n=3)
vectorizer = TfidfVectorizer(min_df=1, analyzer=ngrams, lowercase=False)
tfidf = vectorizer.fit_transform(skills)
from sklearn.neighbors import NearestNeighbors
nbrs = NearestNeighbors(n_neighbors=1, n_jobs=-1).fit(tfidf)
```

E. Deployment and Rendering

At last deployment and rendering is done using Flask and simple Html templates.

VI. RESULTS

Here the skills of a person are inputted manually and after using NLP techniques including vectorization a list of jobs are recommended from the provided dataset of job listings.

index	Position	Company	Location
0 1213	Senior Member Technical Staff - Modeling Engineering	Rambus	Bengaluru
1 1703	Cloud Foundry / Java Full Stack Developer-ICD Cloud Development	SAP	Bengaluru
2 1394	UI Developer	Prowess India	Bengaluru
3 221	Software Test Automation Engineer	Red Lion Controls, Inc.	- Pune
4 1121	Sr Member Technical Staff - Modeling Engineering	Rambus	Bengaluru
5 1252	Senior Machine Learning Engineer	Bengaluru	Bengaluru
6 1274	Data Analyst Consumption Insights	Autodesk	Bengaluru
7 1273	Scientist, Protein Biology	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Bengaluru
8 1247	Data Analyst	Dotball Interactive	Bengaluru
9 1272	Data Analyst	Myra	Bengaluru

Fig 2: Result page showing suggested jobs

VII. CONCLUSIONS

To sum up, the job recommendation system created with skill-based input and Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a state-of-the-art response to the contemporary labor market. The system provides a highly personalized, accurate, and efficient method of matching job seekers with relevant employment opportunities by utilizing natural language processing (NLP). This promotes diversity, fills skills gaps, saves time and resources for both companies and job seekers, and provides real-time job updates. The project is a valuable resource for empowering job seekers and supporting employers in their talent acquisition efforts. Its data-driven insights and customized recommendations ultimately lead to a more effective and fulfilling hiring process.

VIII. REFERENCES

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